

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES IN 1.0 M POTASSIUM CHLORIDE

	Ce(III)	Crotonic acid		Cinnamic acid		Itaconic acid		Citraconic acid	
		1:1		1:1		1:1		1:1	
		25°	35°	25°	35°	25°	35°	25°	35°
Metal-ligand stability constant (log K)	Ce(III)	2.76	2.61	2.91	2.50	3.50	3.14	3.82	3.41
Change in enthalpy (ΔH) in k cal/mole	Ce(III)		-6.33*		-17.13*		-15.20*		-17.31*
Change in free energy (ΔG) in k cal/mole	Ce(III)	-3.78	-2.92	-3.99	-3.54	-4.80	-4.50	-5.24	-4.83
Change in entropy (ΔS) in cal/degree/mole	Ce(III)	-8.55	-11.07	-44.69	-44.77	-34.89	-34.90	-40.57	-40.52

* For the difference of 10°.

mercury. Dissolved oxygen was removed by passing pure nitrogen gas through the solution before recording the polarograms. An Elico digital pH meter (Model LI-120) was used to adjust the pH of the test solution at 2.75 ± 0.02 . All measurements were made at 25 and 35° by the use of thermostat.

Results and Discussion

Ce(III) gave a well defined reversible reduction wave at $pH 2.75 \pm 0.02^{6-7}$ in 1.0 M potassium chloride with 0.01% gelatin being used as a maximum suppressor. The log plot slope comes to the order of 20 ± 1 mV for Ce(III) and its complexes with all the four ligands indicating reversibility of the electrode process. The nature of the waves for metal ion and its complexes was found to be diffusion controlled as revealed from the straight line plots of i_d vs \sqrt{t} . The reduction potential of Ce(III) at $pH 2.75 \pm 0.02$ was -1.85 V vs SCE.

The half wave potential shifted to more negative value on increasing the concentration of ligand⁸. A Lingane treatment of the data revealed the formation of 1:1 complexes of Ce(III) with all the four ligands. The thermodynamic parameters were calculated from the thermodynamic relations⁹. Stability constants and thermodynamic parameters are tabulated in Table 1.

The order of stability constants of the complexes is

$$[Ce(III) - (crotonate)]^{2+} < [Ce(III) - (cinnamate)]^{2+} \\ \log k \quad 2.76 \quad 2.91 \\ \text{at } 25^\circ \\ < [Ce(III) - (itaconate)]^1 < [Ce(III) - (citraconate)]^1 \\ \quad 3.50 \quad 3.82$$

It is evident from the above that $[Ce(III) - (crotonate)]^{2+}$ is less stable than $[Ce(III) - (cinnamate)]^{2+}$. Both the ligands being monodentate in nature form simple coordination compounds while itaconic acid and citraconic acid being bidentate in nature form chelate compounds, which accounts for their higher stability over monodentate ligands¹⁰. The lower stability of the itaconate complex as compared to citraconate complex can be due to the presence of double bond in the ring¹¹.

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Polarographic Determination of Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of the Complexes of Nd(III) with Hydroxylamine, Hydrazine and Phenylhydrazine

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HYDROXYLAMINE, hydrazine and phenylhydrazine are the derivatives of ammonia which have been used as complexing agents by different workers¹⁻⁴. However, the use of polarography for the complexation study of rare earths with these ligands has not been reported. The stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of the com-

TABLE 1—METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES AT $\mu=1.0 M$ POTASSIUM CHLORIDE

	Nd(III)	Hydrazine 1:1		Hydroxylamine 1:1		Phenylhydrazine 1:1	
		25°	35°	25°	35°	25°	35°
Metal-ligand stability constants (log k)	Nd(III)	4.97	4.12	3.87	3.55	3.42	3.13
Change in enthalpy (ΔH) in k cal/mole	Nd(III)	-10.59*		-18.09*		-12.24*	
Change in free energy (ΔG) in k cal/mole	Nd(III)	-5.99	-5.83	-5.30	-5.04	-4.69	-4.43
Change in entropy (ΔS) in cal/degree/mole	Nd(III)	-12.46	-15.61	-26.13	-26.39	-25.93	-25.36

The order of stability constants was found to be
 $Nd(C_6H_5NHNH_2)^{3+} < Nd(NH_2OH)^{3+} < Nd(N_2H_4)^{3+}$.

* For the difference of 10°.

plexes of Nd(III) with these derivative of ammonia on a dropping mercury electrode have been studied and the results are presented here.

Experimental

A. R. grade chemicals were used to prepare the solutions. The solutions of ligands were prepared by dissolving the calculated quantities of hydrazine hydrochloride, hydroxylamine hydrochloride and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (Chroma-Gesellschaft Schmid and Co., Germany) in double distilled water. The metal solution was prepared by dissolving the metal oxide in hydrochloric acid and was standardized with EDTA⁵.

In the test electrolytic solution, the concentrations of Nd(III), potassium chloride and gelatin were 2.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01%, respectively. The concentration of ligand was varied from 1.0 mM to 10.0 mM in each case. Ionic strength was fixed at $\mu=1.0$ adjusted with potassium chloride. Sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid was used to adjust the pH of the test solution at 2.4 ± 0.02 .

Polarograms were recorded on an automatic pen recording (C.I.C., Baroda, India) polarograph, the capillary used had an in value of 2.15 mg/sec, and drop time of 3.1 sec at 44.0 cm effective height of the mercury ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.15 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$). Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the solution for removing the dissolved oxygen. An Elico digital pH meter (Model LI-120) was used to measure the pH of the solution. All the measurements were carried out at 25 and 35° by the use of a thermostat.

Results and Discussion

Nd(III) gives a well defined three electron reversible reduction wave at pH $2.4 \pm 0.02^{6-7}$ in 1.0 M potassium chloride, with 0.01% gelatin being used as a maximum suppressor. The log plot slopes comes to the order of 20 ± 1 mV for Nd(III) and its complexes with all the three ligands indicating reversibility of the electrode process. The nature of the waves for metal ion and its complexes was found to be diffusion controlled as revealed from the straight line plots of i_d vs \sqrt{t} . The reduction potential of Nd(III) at pH 2.40 ± 0.02 was -1.79 V vs SCE.

The half wave potential shifted to more negative value on increasing the concentration of ligand. A

Lingane⁸ treatment of the data revealed the formation of 1:1 complexes of Nd(III) with all the three ligands. The thermodynamic parameters were calculated from the thermodynamic relations⁹ and are given in Table 1.

Hydrazine is more basic¹⁰⁻¹¹ than hydroxylamine. This explains the higher stability of $Nd(N_2H_4)^{3+}$ than $Nd(NH_2OH)^{3+}$. The heavy benzene nucleus in phenylhydrazine is responsible for the lesser stability of its complex with Nd(III).

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Dielectric and Ultraviolet Studies of Molecular Complexes in *n*-Butanol-Carbonyl Systems

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GENERALLY, the short range interactions like hydrogen bonding between a proton donor and an acceptor lead to an increased polarity of the bond¹ and hence the dipole moment of the adduct will